

CHEMISTRY OF SUBSTITUTED RING COMPOUNDS. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ TRIMETHYLCYCLOPENTANONE.

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Synthesis of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone has been effected from $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid. The acid has been synthesised by two independent processes. In one of these mesitonic ester has been allowed to react with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of magnesium yielding a lactonic ester. From this the chloro-ester has been obtained which on reduction gives the substituted adipic ester. In the second method mesitonic ester has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate and the unsaturated ester, thus prepared, gives the saturated compound which ultimately produces $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic ester. The ketone has been found to be identical with that prepared by Wallach by the degradation of dimethyldihydroisophorone.

The exact nature of "steric influence" of alkyl substituents on alicyclic rings has not yet been very clearly understood. It is proposed in this series of papers to examine the influence of various alkyl as well as aryl substituents on the formation and stability of some of these ring systems. It is also proposed to examine here incidentally, the influence, if any, that may be brought about in altering the specific character of a definite type of ring compound by different substituents.

It has been observed that by the introduction of methyl groups into a cyclohexane ring, its influence is altered to a marked extent, as has been found in its influence on the tautomeric nature of *p*-methylcyclohexane-1-acetyl-1-malonic acid (Quadrat-i-Khuda and Mukherji, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 570). It may, therefore, be expected that by an examination of the differently substituted cyclopentanones, as well as cyclohexanones, some valuable informations may be obtained, at least so far as the influence of substituents is concerned. For this purpose several differently substituted cyclopentanones have been synthesised. Of these in the present paper is described the synthesis of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone (V), some of whose derivatives may give the necessary information.

Wallach prepared two trimethylcyclopentanones; one by the internal condensation of the diketone (I) (*Annalen*, 1916, 408, 204) and subsequent reduction, while the other by the degradation of the dibromide of dihydroisophorone (VI) (*Annalen*, 1918, 414, 328); the former of which he represented by the formula (V) and the latter by the formula (XIII). Both the methods are, however, ambiguous. The first method may yield $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone (V) as well as $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone (IV) respectively, from the initial condensation products (III) or (II).

The second should also give two ketones, according as the dibromide of dihydro-isophorone is either (VII) or (VIII), which may give the diketone (IX) or (X) and the decomposition of these would lead to the formation of the hydroxy acids (XI) or (XII), which should produce the ketones (XIII) or (V) respectively. The actual experiment, however, gives only one product leaving its identity uncertain.

It is not, therefore, surprising that Wallach was led to a wrong conclusion.

The method employed by us does not leave any room for doubt, regarding the constitution of the ketone (V). From evidences, now accumulated, we are led to suggest that the ketone prepared by Wallach from dihydroisophorone should be represented by the formula (V) and not by (XIII) as suggested by him. By the decomposition of the dibromodihydroisophorone by alkali and subsequent treatment with lead peroxide, Wallach (*loc. cit.*) obtained a ketone that gave a semicarbazone melting at 173° , which is the melting point of the semicarbazone of our ketone (V) (mixed m. p.). Hence, the dibromodihydroisophorone and the diketone should respectively be (VIII) and (X).

The synthesis of $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipic acid has been carried out by two different methods.

(a) Mesitonic ester prepared by the modification of the method of Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1219), when acted upon by ethyl bromoacetate in presence of magnesium, gives the lactonic ester (XIV) in good yield. This has been treated with phosphorus pentachloride and the intermediate chloro-acid chloride with absolute alcohol gives ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyl- γ -chloroadipate (XV). This on reduction gives the adipic ester (XVI).

(XIV)

(XV)

(XVI)

(b) The same ester has also been prepared by condensing mesitonic ester with ethyl cyanoacetate and reducing the unsaturated ester (XVII) with aluminium amalgam when (XVIII) has been obtained.

(XVII)

(XVIII)

in ether, washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and the solvent removed. The remaining oil was fractionated under reduced pressure when a fraction distilled at $115-16^{\circ}/30-32$ mm. and weighed 30 g. This on being redistilled boiled at $90^{\circ}/7$ mm. The higher fraction, b.p. $140-50^{\circ}/35$ mm. solidified in the receiver, yield 18 g.

The first fraction gave a semicarbazone which, when crystallised from methyl alcohol, melted at 165° and was identified to be that of mesitonic ester. (Found : C, 52.2 ; H, 8.3. $C_{10}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires C, 52.4 ; H, 8.3 per cent). The ester when regenerated from the semicarbazone had $d_4^{32.8}$, 0.96095 ; $n_D^{32.8}$, 1.41576, whence $[R_L]_D$, 44.9 (calc. 45.3). This was hydrolysed by aqueous hydrochloric acid when an acid, m.p. 72° , was obtained. It gave a semicarbazone, m.p. 196° . The acid possessed all the properties assigned to it by Pinner (*Ber.*, 1881, **14**, 1072 ; 1882, **15**, 585) and Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 1219).

The second fraction consisted of the ester of mesitylic acid and gave mesitylic acid on hydrolysis. It was recrystallised from water when it melted at 173° . (Found : C, 56.07 ; H, 7.65. $C_8H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 56.14 ; H, 7.6 per cent).

Ethyl α -Trimethylbutyrolactone- γ -acetate (XIV).—Magnesium turnings (4.3 g.) were added to a mixture of mesitonic ester (25.8 g.) and ethyl bromoacetate (25.1 g.) in dry benzene (80 c.c.). A vigorous reaction started after heating the mixture for 5 minutes on a steam-bath. This was allowed to proceed as vigorously as was consistent with safety, and heating on the water-bath was continued for 3 hours when the magnesium dissolved completely. The mass was decomposed with ice and dilute sulphuric acid, and the benzene layer was separated, washed successively with dilute sulphuric acid (10%) sodium hydroxide (10%) and water. It was then dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and the solvent removed under reduced pressure (40-45 mm.) on a water-bath. The residual oil on being fractionated gave the lactonic ester, b. p. $148-50^{\circ}/7$ mm., yield 17 g. The subsequent fraction, b.p. $170-75^{\circ}/6$ mm. (thick liquid, yield 2 g.), has not yet been investigated.

The lactonic ester on redistillation boiled at $148-50^{\circ}/7$ mm. It is a colourless mobile liquid, insoluble in water ; $d_4^{31.2}$, 1.0471 ; $n_D^{31.2}$, 1.44355, whence $[R_L]_D$, 54.2 (calc. 54.11). (Found : C, 61.5 ; H, 8.3. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 61.7 ; H, 8.41 per cent).

Ethyl α -Trimethyl- γ -chloroadipate (XV).—The lactonic ester (12 g.) was heated with phosphorus pentachloride (26 g.) for 3 hours on a steam-bath when a clear solution was obtained. The whole was then cooled well and poured gradually into well cooled absolute alcohol (75 c.c.) and after

standing overnight, a little water was added to it when an oil separated which was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed successively with dilute sodium carbonate and water, dried over calcium chloride, the solvent removed and the residual oil carefully distilled under reduced pressure from a glycerine bath. The chloro-ester came over at $113-15^{\circ}/5\text{mm.}$, yield 78%. It is a colourless mobile liquid having $d_4^{31.5}$, 1.0381; $n_D^{31.5}$, 1.43913, whence $[R_L]_D$, 70.6 (calc. 70.4). (Found: Cl, 12.45. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$ requires Cl, 12.5 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethyladipate (XVI).—Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyl- γ -chloroadipate (20 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (290 c.c.) and heated on a sand-bath with a reflux condenser. Zinc dust (40 g.) was added to the hot solution in small portions with frequent shaking during 10 hours. Heating was continued for another 10 hours. The solution was decanted off from the lumps of zinc. Any substance adhering to the lumps was washed away with ether. The solution was cooled in ice, just neutralised with caustic soda solution and thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with little water, dried and the solvent removed. The ester distilled at $164^{\circ}/44-45\text{ mm.}$, yield 8 g.; when redistilled it came over at $145-146^{\circ}/16\text{ mm.}$ It is a colourless mobile liquid and has d_4^{32} , 0.99383; n_D^{32} , 1.44335, whence $[R_L]_D$ 65.3 (calc. 65.6). (Found: C, 63.6; H, 9.5. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 63.9; H, 9.8 per cent).

$\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethyladipic Acid (XIX).—Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipate (XVI) (8 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (15%, 300 c.c.) by refluxing on a sand-bath for 12 hours. The solution was then evaporated to a small bulk on a water-bath, neutralised with sodium carbonate solution, the unhydrolysed ester removed by ether and the solution was then evaporated almost to dryness, cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acid separating was carefully extracted with ether the ethereal extract kept overnight with anhydrous sodium sulphate in contact with animal charcoal. The filtrate on removal of ether, gave a heavy oil which solidified on cooling. It was dried in a desiccator and crystallised from dry ether, m. p. 80° . (Found: C, 57.19; H, 8.2. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 57.4; H, 8.5 per cent).

Ethyl α -Cyano- $\beta\delta\delta$ -trimethyl- Δ^a -butene- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (XVII).—This was prepared by some modification of the method of Bardhan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1852). To a mixture of mesitonic ester (114.6 g.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (75.4 g.) were added piperidine (6 c.c.) and anhydrous sodium sulphate (25 g.). After keeping the mixture overnight at the room temperature it was heated on a water-bath for 30 hours, a fresh quantity of sodium sulphate (15 g.) was then added and the heating continued for

another 30 hours. The cold product was poured into water, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the heavy oil taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate, dried and fractionated under reduced pressure. At first some unchanged ketonic ester and cyano-ester came over. The unsaturated cyano-ester distilled at $158-64^{\circ}/4$ mm. The mixture of unchanged ketonic ester and cyanoacetic ester was again mixed with 3 c.c. of piperidine and sodium sulphate (10 g.) and treated as before. The process was repeated several times, and the combined high boiling fraction was purified by redistillation under reduced pressure. From the above quantities the total yield was 98 g. When redistilled the unsaturated cyano-ester boiled at $162^{\circ}/4$ mm. It is a colourless heavy oil having $d_4^{32.8}$, 1.0431; $n_D^{32.8}$, 1.45717, whence $[R_L]_D$, 69.68 (calc. 69.4). (Found: C, 62.8; H, 8.05. $C_{14}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 62.9; H, 7.86 per cent).

Ethyl α -Cyano- $\beta\delta\delta$ -trimethylbutane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (XVIII).—Aluminium amalgam, prepared from aluminium foil (200 g.), was taken in a flask fitted with a tap-funnel and an efficient condenser and covered with moist ether (400 c.c.) and the ethereal solution of ethyl α -cyano- $\beta\delta\delta$ -trimethyl- Δ^a -butene- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (20 g.) was added as quickly as possible; vigorous boiling ensued and the reaction slackened after some time. Water (1 or 2 c.c.) was then added at times to accelerate the reaction. The contents were shaken frequently. The reaction gradually slackened after about 9 hours. The very slow reaction was allowed to proceed overnight. The ethereal solution was decanted and the slimy residue was thoroughly extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and on removing the solvent a thick liquid was obtained which was subjected to the same reduction process once again to effect complete reduction. The ester was finally fractionated under reduced pressure when the saturated cyano-ester boiled at $148-52^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 9 g. On redistillation it was obtained as a thick colourless liquid, b. p. $155-56^{\circ}/8$ mm. It had d_4^{82} , 1.0230, n_D^{32} , 1.44033; whence $[R_L]_D$, 69.4 (calc. 69.6). (Found: C, 62.1; H, 8.3. $C_{14}H_{23}O_4N$ requires C, 62.4; H, 8.5 per cent).

$\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethyladipic Acid (XIX).—Ethyl α -cyanotrimethylbutane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (20 g.), mixed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (d 1.21, 400 c.c.) was refluxed for 35 hours. This was then evaporated to a small bulk and neutralised with sodium carbonate solution. The unreacted ester was washed with ether and the aqueous solution was evaporated to dryness. The mass was cooled in ice, acidified with hydro-

chloric acid and extracted five times with ether. The ethereal solution was dried and the solvent removed, when an oily mass was obtained, which solidified on keeping in an evacuated desiccator. On crystallisation from dry ether it melted at 80° and was found to be identical with the acid described before (mixed m. p. 80°).

Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone- δ -carboxylate (XX).—Sodium (2.3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethyladipate (21.5 g.) was added to the well cooled sodium ethoxide solution with constant shaking. The mixture was refluxed for 6 hours on a steam-bath. The product was cooled in ice, decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. After removal of ether, alcohol was removed under reduced pressure. Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone- δ -carboxylate distilled as a colourless liquid, b. p., $88-90^{\circ}/5$ mm; $d_4^{31.8}$, 0.98559; $n_D^{31.8}$, 1.43882, whence $[R_L]_D$, 52.85 (calc. 52.5), yield 8.5 g. (48.7%). (Found: C, 66.38; H, 8.82. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.7; H, 8.9 per cent). It gives a distinct pink colouration with ferric chloride solution.

$\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -Trimethylcyclopentanone (V).—Ethyl $\alpha\alpha\gamma$ -trimethylcyclopentanone- δ -carboxylate (8.5 g.) was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:3, 100 c.c.) and refluxed for 2 hours. The acid was neutralised with strong sodium carbonate solution and the oil that separated was taken up in ether and on removing the solvent the residual liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure. The ketone distilled at $65-66^{\circ}/45$ mm.; $d_4^{32.8}$, 0.87660, $n_D^{32.8}$, 1.42426, whence $[R_L]_D$, 36.68 (calc. 36.9); yield 2 g. (45.5%) (Found: C, 75.8; H, 10.9. $C_8H_{14}O$ requires C, 76.19; H, 11.1 per cent). It was found to possess distinct camphoraceous odour. The semicarbazone of the ketone was readily obtained as colourless shining flakes from methyl alcohol. When recrystallised from methyl alcohol it melts at 173° . (Found: C, 58.8; H, 9.2. $C_9H_{17}ON_3$ requires C, 59.0; H, 9.29 per cent). The trimethylcyclopentanone yielded a characteristic monobenzylidene compound (XXI), which when crystallised from petrol melted at $125-26^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 83.78; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.1; H, 8.4 per cent).

Wallach's Ketone.—Dibromodihydroisophoroné (VII) was prepared by the action of dry bromine (12 c.c.) on a solution of dihydroisophorone (10 g.) in dry carbon disulphide (30 c.c.). The bromination proceeded quite easily with the production of 19 g. of dibromodihydroisophorone. After two crystallisations from methyl alcohol, it melted at 90° (cf. Wallach, *loc. cit.*).

Dibromodihydroisophorone (25 g.) was shaken with a solution of potassium hydroxide (17 g.) in water (667 c.c.) for 6 hours and the diketone was isolated from the solid after acidification with hydrochloric acid by distillation in a current of steam. The diketone (X) separated as a light yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 168-69° and not at 89-90° as mentioned by Wallach. (Found: C, 69.7 ; H, 8.9. $C_9H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 70.08; H, 9.1 per cent). The diketone (10 g.) gave trimethylhydroxycyclopentane-carboxylic acid (XII) on being heated in a sealed tube with 50 c.c. of potassium hydroxide solution (1:2) at about 140° for 4 hours and after usual purification melted at 90°. When treated with lead peroxide as described by Wallach, it gave the ketone (V) which yielded a semicarbazone, m. p. 173°, as in the previous case.

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